

Mulching and weed management effects on performance of minimum tillage unpuddled transplanted rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Abstract

Conservation tillage technology based on mulch retention are being developed in Bangladesh but the optimum weed control for crops in the cropping sequence is still not well defined. The present experiment aimed to determine the effect of mulch retention, herbicides and hand weeding on weed control in unpuddled rice transplanted after mustard in *mustard-boro rice-t. aman rice* system at farmers field during *Boro* season (January to May) in the year of 2014 and 2015. Rice cv. *BRR1 dhan28*, was transplanted with six tillage and weed control practices *viz.*, Conventional tillage (CT) + farmer's weeding practice (Control); Roundup (RU) + Strip tillage (ST) + 1 hand weeding; RU + ST + Pre-emergence (PE) herbicide (Pendimethalin); RU + ST + Post-emergence (PO) herbicide (Ethoxy-sulfuran); RU+ ST + PE + PO; RU+ ST + weed-free (WF), and two levels of mustard mulch *viz.*, no mulch and 50% mulch (875 kg ha⁻¹). Two years research data reveals, CT produced about 30% higher weed density and 40% higher biomass compared to ST. Spraying PE followed by PO performed the best over single of each and manual weeding which reduced density by 40% in 2014 and 50% in 2015 and biomass by 70% in both the year. Mulch reduced weed density by 20% in 2014 and 16% in 2015 and biomass by 27% and 34%, respectively. There was no significant yield difference between CT and ST but in association with weed control and mulching practices, tillage types offered significant yield variation. ST kept WF yielded the highest which was 30% higher in 2014 and 23% higher in 2015 over control. The highest BCR of about 50% higher over control was calculated from ST sprayed the PE followed by PO in both the year. Mulch increased crop yield and BCR by 4% and 9%, respectively. The highest and about 30% higher grain over the interaction of CT without mulch was yielded from the interaction of ST kept WF retained 50% mulch. The highest BCR of 40% higher over CT without mulch was calculated from the interaction of ST sprayed PE followed by PO retained 50% mulch.

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